

Studies of chelates of cobalt-, nickel-, copper-, zinc- and cadmium(II) with 4-amino-3,5-dioxo-6-methyl-2,3,4,5-tetrahydro-1,2,4-triazine

L. K. Mishra^a, Y. Jha^a, B. K. Sinha^b, R. Kant^b and Rajeshwar Singh^{*c}

^aDepartment of Chemistry, Science College, Patna-800 005, India

^bChemistry Department, P.G.M.U., Bodh-Gaya-824 234, India

^cChemistry Department, Nalanda College, Biharsharif-803 101, India

Manuscript received 22 December 1997, revised 5 June 1998, accepted 22 July 1998

Complexes of some bivalent metal ions with 4-amino-3,5-dioxo-6-methyl-2,3,4,5-tetrahydro-1,2,4-triazine (H-aomtzt) of compositions $M(\text{aomtzt})_2 \cdot n\text{H}_2\text{O}$ ($M = \text{Co}, \text{Ni}, \text{Cu}, \text{Zn}$ or $\text{Cd}; n = 0$ or 2), $M(\text{H-aomtzt})_2\text{Cl}_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ ($M = \text{Co}$ or Ni) and $\text{Cu}(\text{H-aomtzt})\text{Cl}_2$ have been prepared. The results indicate octahedral geometry for Ni^{II} and Co^{II} , tetragonally distorted octahedral for Cu^{II} and tetrahedral for Zn^{II} and Cd^{II} complexes.

We reported earlier¹ the complexes of some bivalent metal ions with 4-amino-5-oxo-3-thioxo-6-methyl/aryl-2,3, 4,5-tetrahydro-1,2,4-triazine (H-aotmtz). Here we report the complexes of oxygen analog of H-aotmtz, 4-amino-3,5-dioxo-6-methyl-2,3,4,5-tetrahydro-1,2,4-triazine (H-aomtzt) with Co^{II} , Ni^{II} , Cu^{II} , Zn^{II} and Cd^{II} .

Results and Discussion

In alkaline medium (pH 10) the ligand (H-aomtzt) is deprotonated via enolisation and forms neutral bischelates of composition, $M(\text{aomtzt})_2 \cdot n\text{H}_2\text{O}$ ($M = \text{Co}^{\text{II}}, \text{Ni}^{\text{II}}, \text{Cu}^{\text{II}}, \text{Zn}^{\text{II}}$ or $\text{Cd}^{\text{II}}; n = 0$ or 2). In weakly acidic medium the ligand coordinates as a neutral chelating molecule forming complexes of compositions, $M(\text{H-aomtzt})_2\text{Cl}_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ ($M = \text{Co}^{\text{II}}$ or Ni^{II}) and $\text{Cu}(\text{aomtzt})\text{Cl}_2$. The inner chelates are insoluble in water and common organic solvents but dissolve appreciably in DMF. The DMF solutions of these chelates are non-conducting indicating their non-electrolytic nature. The chloro complexes of Co^{II} , Ni^{II} and Cu^{II} dissolve in DMF and hot water as well. The DMF solution of $\text{Cu}(\text{H-aomtzt})\text{Cl}_2$ is non-conducting while that of Co^{II} and Ni^{II} shows electrical conductance value in the range $180\text{--}185 \Omega^{-1} \text{mol}^{-1} \text{cm}^2$, suggesting their ionic nature² and the presence of chloride ions in solution. The aquo complexes do not lose water molecules below 110° , indicating their involvement in coordination or presence as lattice water. As expected the Zn^{II} and Cd^{II} complexes are diamagnetic whereas the complexes of Co^{II} , Ni^{II} and Cu^{II} paramagnetic. The room temperature magnetic moment values for the Co^{II} (5.01–5.12), Ni^{II} (3.21–3.34) and Cu^{II} (1.85–1.96

B.M.) complexes suggest their spin-free octahedral geometry³.

The electronic spectra of the Co^{II} and Ni^{II} complexes suggest their octahedral geometry^{4,5}. The reflectance bands observed at 24920 , 15760 and 9050 cm^{-1} for chloronickel(II) complex while those for neutral nickel(II) complex at 24380 , 15950 and 9250 cm^{-1} can be assigned to ${}^3A_{2g} \rightarrow {}^3T_{1g}(P)$, ${}^3A_{2g} \rightarrow {}^3T_{1g}(F)$ and ${}^3A_{2g} \rightarrow {}^3T_{2g}(F)$ transitions in octahedral field. The lower β value for the neutral Ni^{II} complex (0.812) than that of the chloro- Ni^{II} complex indicates enhanced covalency in the neutral chelate. The reflectance bands for the neutral as well as chloro- Co^{II} complexes at $20250\text{--}19620$ and $8950\text{--}8840 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ are assigned to ${}^4T_{1g} \rightarrow {}^4T_{1g}(P)$ and ${}^4T_{1g} \rightarrow {}^4T_{2g}(F)$ transitions respectively, in distorted octahedral ligand field. The unusual high intensity of spectral bands can be attributed to a large tetragonal distortion from octahedral field. The neutral Cu^{II} complex displaying a medium band at 19540 cm^{-1} and a broad asymmetric band at 13800 cm^{-1} are assigned to ${}^2B_{1g} \rightarrow {}^2A_{1g}$ and combination of ${}^2B_{1g} \rightarrow {}^2B_{2g}$ and ${}^2B_{1g} \rightarrow {}^2E_g$ transitions respectively, in tetragonal field. The yellowish green chloro- Cu^{II} complex showed a strong band at 25650 cm^{-1} and a broad weak band near 12800 cm^{-1} . The former band can be attributed to charge transfer mixed up with ${}^2B_{1g} \rightarrow A_{1g}$ transition while the latter is assigned to a combination of ${}^2B_{1g} \rightarrow {}^2B_{2g}$, 2E_g transitions in tetragonally distorted octahedral field⁶. From stoichiometry a more favoured tetrahedral geometry is suggested for the Zn^{II} and Cd^{II} complexes⁷.

The ir bands observed at 3375 and 3100 cm^{-1} in the free ligand are assigned to $\nu_{\text{as}}(\text{NH}_2)$ and $\nu_{\text{s}}(\text{NH}_2)$ vibrations. The medium ligand band at 3250 cm^{-1} (NH) disappeared in the neutral chelates but retained in the chloro-complexes. In the complexes, $\nu_{\text{as}}(\text{NH}_2)$ is enveloped with $\nu(\text{H}_2\text{O})$ of coordinated or lattice water molecules and occurred as a medium broad band at $3420 \pm 20 \text{ cm}^{-1}$. However, $\nu_{\text{s}}(\text{NH}_2)$ is observed near $3020 \pm 20 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ in the com-

plexes. The red-shift⁸ of $\nu_s(\text{NH}_2)$ in the complexes indicates bonding of amino-nitrogen atom of the ligand with the metal ions. The NH_2 deformation vibrations (δNH_2 and βNH_2) observed at 1640 and 1395 cm^{-1} in free ligand are shifted to lower frequencies in the complexes, supporting the coordination of (NH_2) nitrogen atom. The $\delta(\text{NH})$ of free ligand (1506 cm^{-1}) remained unaffected in the chloro-complexes whereas it disappeared in the neutral complexes. The $\nu(\text{C}=\text{O})$ of free ligand observed at 1760 cm^{-1} shifted to lower frequency and appeared as a broad band at 1720–1660 cm^{-1} in the chloro-complexes but it disappeared in the neutral chelates. The red-shift⁹ indicates coordination of carbonyl oxygen atom in the chloro-complexes, while disappearance of $\nu(\text{C}=\text{O})$ vibration indicates coordination of oxygen atom via enolisation and deprotonation in the neutral complexes. In the neutral complexes a number of ir bands disappeared due to disappearance of ring (NH) and amide (CO) groups. The deformation band of H_2O merged with $\delta(\text{NH}_2)$ near 1630 cm^{-1} in the complexes. The new medium band observed at 680–630 cm^{-1} in the Co^{II} , Ni^{II} and Cu^{II} complexes is assigned to rocking vibration of coordinated water molecules^{8,9}. A new band of medium to strong intensity found at $1170 \pm 10 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ in the neutral chelates is attributed to $\nu(\text{C}-\text{O})$ of deprotonated enolic amide group¹⁰. The other ligand bands observed at 1305, 1240, 1200, 1110, 1010, 990, 910, 810, 760 and 740 cm^{-1} due to (NH_2) wagging, rocking, (CH_3) bending, ring stretches, NH and $\text{C}-\text{H}$ out-of-plane bending vibrations¹¹, are not affected appreciably in the complexes. In far-ir region, the new bands observed at 450 ± 13 and $370 \pm 10 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ in the complexes are assigned to $\nu(\text{M}-\text{O})$ and $\nu(\text{M}-\text{N})$ vibrations¹² respectively. In the chloro-complex of Cu^{II} , an additional medium band found at 325 cm^{-1} is assigned to $\text{Cu}-\text{Cl}$ stretching vibration¹².

Experimental

The ligand (H-aomt) was prepared by the reported method¹³. All other chemicals and metal salts used were of AnalaR or E. Merck's extra pure grade. Magnetic susceptibility was measured by Gouy method. Diffuse reflectance spectra were recorded on a Unicam SP 700 spectrophotometer and ir spectra on a Hilger-Watts H800 spectrophotometer at I.I.T., Delhi.

2 or 0) : An ethanolic solution of the ligand (0.01 mol in 40 ml) was added to an aqueous ethanolic solution of the metal acetate hydrates (0.005 mol in 30 ml) and pH of the mixture was raised to 9–10 by adding sodium acetate solution. It was digested on a steam-bath for 0.5 h and the resulting complex was washed with ethanol and dried in a desiccator over anhydrous CaCl_2 .

$M(\text{H-aomt})_2 \cdot \text{Cl}_2 \cdot n\text{H}_2\text{O}$ ($M = \text{Co}^{\text{II}}$ or Ni^{II} ; $n = 2$) and $[\text{Cu}(\text{H-aomt})\text{Cl}_2]$: A mixture of an ethanolic solution of the ligand (0.02 mol in 50 ml) and an ethanolic solution of hydrated metal chloride (0.01 mol in 30 ml) was refluxed on a steam-bath for 1.5 h. It was then cooled and the resulting coloured solid complex was washed with cold ethanol and ether and dried in a desiccator over anhydrous CaCl_2 .

All the complexes gave satisfactory elemental analyses.

References

1. P. D. Singh and L. K. Mishra, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1981, **58**, 1007; 1988, **65**, 21.
2. J. V. Quagliano, J. Fujita, G. Fraz, S. Walmsley, D. J. Phillips and S. Y. Tyree, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1961, **83**, 3770.
3. R. L. Carlin, *Transition Met. Chem.*, 1969, **5**, 1; R. S. Nyholm and B. N. Figgis, *Prog. Inorg. Chem.*, 1964, **6**, 41.
4. A. B. P. Lever, "Inorganic Electronic Spectroscopy", Elsevier, New York, 1968.
5. F. A. Cotton, D. M. L. Goodgame and M. Goodgame, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1961, **83**, 4690.
6. H. Elliott, B. J. Hathaway and R. C. Slade, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1966, **5**, 669.
7. F. A. Cotton and G. Wilkinson, "Advanced Inorganic Chemistry, A Comprehensive Text", Interscience, New York, 1966.
8. K. K. Arbindakshan, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1987, **26**, 241.
9. K. Nakamoto, "The Infrared and Raman Spectra of Inorganic and Coordination Compounds", Wiley-Interscience, New York, 1978.
10. T. J. Lane, I. Nakagawa, J. L. Walter and A. J. Kandathil, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1962, **1**, 267.
11. L. J. Bellamy, "The Infrared Spectra of Complex Molecules", 2nd Ed., Chapman and Hall, London, 1980.
12. D. M. Adams, "Metal-ligand and Related Vibrations", St. Martin's Press, New York, 1968; J. R. Ferraro, "Low Frequency Vibrations of Inorganic and Coordination Compounds", Plenum, New York, 1971.
13. A. Dornow and H. Pietsch, *Chem. Ber.*, 1967, **100**, 2587.